

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

How to convert IRS into a low-amylose variety

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The theoretical base for our experiment to incorporate the low-amylose trait of Taichung 65 into IR36 is provided by the following recent advances in rice genetics:

- Several alleles are at the Wx locus: Wx^a for high amylose content, Wx^b for low amylose, and the wx gene.
- Many *javanica* rices and almost all Japanese rices that are donors of intermediate or low amylose content show semisterility in the F_1 hybrids when crossed with IR varieties because the female gametes possessing S_5^j or a similar allele are aborted due to allelic interaction of S_5^i/S_5^j genotype, where S_5^i is from IR varieties.
- The wx locus is closely linked with the S locus in the first linkage group of rice. Therefore, Wx^b is likely to be eliminated in crosses with IR varieties through the abortion of S_5^j gametes.

The arrangement of relevant genes is in the order of *alk*(alkali digestion)- C^+ (chromogen for apiculus color)- S_5^j - Wx^b in Taichung 65(T65) and of *Alk*- $C^+S_5^i$ - Wx^a in IR36. In the F_1 of T65/IR36, most female gametes carrying S_5^j were eliminated. By backcrossing IR36 to the F_1 , some surviving female gametes with S_5^j and all of the gametes with S_5^i are pollinated by IR36. Thus, from 94 B_1F_1 plants of T65/IR36//IR36, some plants with C^+ and lower fertility which indicated S_5^i/S_5^j genotype were chosen for another backcross by IR36. Some characters of the selected B_1F_1 plants are shown in Table 1. By the marker genes, the possibility to recover Wx^b was predicted, because those plants with d

Table 1. Some characters of plants selected from the B_1F_1 of T65/IR36//IR36 for backcrossing by IR36. TARC, Japan.

Plant no.	Spikelet fertility ^a (%)	Genotype for <i>alk</i>	Genotype for C^+	Assumed gene arrangement ^b	Possibility for Wx^b
1	65.6	+/+	C^+	<i>Alk-x-C⁺-S^j-</i>	+
2	80.2†	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-x-Sⁱ-</i>	-
3	63.1	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-S^j-</i>	+
4	57.7	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-S^j-</i>	+
5	79.8†	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-x-Sⁱ-</i>	-
6	28.2	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-S^j-</i>	+
7	82.2 †	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-x-Sⁱ-</i>	-
8	61.2	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-S^j-</i>	+
9	69.3	+/+	C^+	<i>Alk-x-C⁺-S^j-</i>	+
10	40.3	+/ <i>alk</i>	C^+	<i>alk-C⁺-S^j-</i>	+

^a† shows nearly normal fertility, indicating the effect of S^i after the recombination of C^+ and S^i .
^bx marks the point of assumed crossing over.

Table 2. Characteristics of cooked rice of the selected B_2F_2 plants of T65/IR36//IR36. TARC, Japan.

Plant no.	Genotype for <i>alk</i>	Plants (no.) in each class			Spikelet fertility
		Sticky	Segregating	Nonsticky	
1	+/+	8	5	10	Slightly low
2	+/ <i>alk</i>		9	9	Normal
3	+/+	3	6	3	Normal
4	+/ <i>alk</i>	1	5	2	Normal
5	+/ <i>alk</i>		6		Normal
6	+/ <i>alk</i>	1			Normal
7	+/+	1	2	4	Normal
8	+/ <i>alk</i>	4	7	4	Normal
9	+/ <i>alk</i>	2	1	7	Normal
10		No plant was selected			

and S (indicated by low fertility) are likely to possess Wx^b due to linkage.

About 30 B_2F_1 plants from each of the 10 B_2F_1 crosses were raised during winter 1984-85, and from each B_2F_1 population the plants with C^+ were bulk harvested to grow a B_2F_2 population of 50 plants. Many B_2F_2 plants showed normal fertility. The selected ones showed normal fertility; they were individually harvested and their cooked rice was tested. By cooking small amounts of milled rice in test tubes and tasting the cooked samples, the presence of Wx^b was determined (Table 2). Many plants of IR36 type were found to have sticky cooked rice. The recovery of low-amylose genotype in the B_2F_2 matched the expectation in B_1F_1 stage (Table 1).

The preliminary trial demonstrated that many plants with low amylose content can be recovered after two backcrossing of IR36, which is a high-amylose variety. Although we did not handle varieties with intermediate amylose, the principle can be applied for incorporating intermediate amylose content into high yielding varieties the quality of which is not always preferred. *J*

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